

Studies with Gwendolyn Koldofsky at the University of Southern California Deon Nielsen Price Reminisces

“Change the color!” Madame K said as I sat at the piano for the first time and played the first chord of an art song. What?! I had sometimes been admonished to play softer or louder or more legato, but never before had I been directed to change the color of the piano tone. I believe that command set the tone of my five years (1972 – 1977) of intense, challenging and adventurous study with the remarkable artist and teacher, Gwendolyn Koldofsky.

Several more of her directions have remained vivid in my mind throughout the nearly 50 years since completing my Doctor of Musical Arts in Collaborative Piano (then called Accompanying):

“There are a hundred ways to play the piano.” — the more you can employ, the more colorful your playing will be.

“Just *pretend* you are playing fortissimo.” —so as to keep the integrity of the mood and tone color of a particular song and not step out of it and into the character of a different work.

“floating arm” —especially in light arpeggiated passages of Brahms and Schumann

“thin fingers” —for many French songs

“Isn’t that why you came to study with me, to learn what I have to offer?” as she dismissed a musical insight of my own that I suggested that countered her view. (I made no more such suggestions!) When collaborating with some of his master class students, I learned that legendary Jascha Heifetz, also on the faculty during those years, had the same attitude. He would say to a violinist, “We do it this way,” and expect the violinist to never vary from it again.

“You are very fortunate to have another side of your life besides music,” she said to me after having met my husband and children at one of my five degree recitals. She said that most of her pianists were driven solely by the emotions of their artistic successes and failures in their music and lacked other sources of emotional support.

“You will be successful because you feel the music with the singer.” She said quietly to me during a coaching session in her home in preparation for concerts of music by Halsey Stevens in celebration of his finally being named Composer-in-Residence after 30 years on the USC faculty.

“This recital is a great accomplishment.” —a rare compliment from Mrs. Koldofsky, following one of my degree recitals, that usually included both solo and collaborative repertoire.

When collaborating with artists, especially singers, I still continue to sense Mrs. Koldofsky hovering over my shoulder dispensing directions in her kind but firm way. When I moved to Arroyo Grande on the Central California Coast in 2020, I met Susan Azaret Davies, who had used my text for pianists, *Accompanying Skills for Pianists, 2nd Edition*, with her students throughout her many years teaching at CalPoly San Luis Obispo. She said that she had also studied with Mrs. Koldofsky and that she loved using the book because in its pages she could again feel Mrs. Koldofsky whispering over her shoulder.

Throughout the five years I participated in the Koldofsky vocal/piano master classes, I was constantly challenged. I often returned home to swim vigorously 10 or 20 laps and wash away my tears. In order to encourage, console, and to help balance my emotions, I would picture myself on a slant board where I could look upward and see the artistic goal way ahead of me, but then also look down and see how far I had come. Mrs. Koldofsky told me that when she was a girl, her teacher (or manager?) scheduled frequent solo piano performances for her. Before each performance he always took her to dinner for a hearty meal of meat and potatoes. She said that throughout her developing years she was always given a project one step more challenging than the one she had just accomplished. I frequently felt challenged in the same way with each the assignment of new song cycle.

During the summer of 1973 or 1974, when my husband and I took our children on an American History tour of the United States, Mrs Koldofsky scheduled appointments for me to interview the collaborative piano faculty chair at five universities. At the University of Michigan, my *alma mater* where I had completed my Master of Music Degree in solo piano, I interviewed Eugene Bossart about his curriculum for collaborative piano. He discussed in depth his program of pairing

the pianists with instrumentalists. When I asked him about accompanying vocalists, he surprised me by saying, that “Oh no!” that he, himself accompanied all the vocalists. He did not train (or trust) the student pianists to collaborate with them. This was interesting to me, personally, because during the year prior to my beginning graduate work there, I had been accompanist for one of the voice studios, and played for those students’ juries and recitals. On our family tour, we visited my sister whose husband was a medical student at Johns Hopkins University in Baltimore Maryland. That gave me the opportunity to spend an enjoyable hour at the Peabody Institute interviewing Ellen Mack, the warm and charismatic chair of collaborative piano. She had studied with Gwendolyn Koldofsky and John Crown at USC where she was pianist for the Jascha Heifetz/Gregor Piatigorsky/William Primrose Institute. The two women were close friends and in frequent communication. I recently learned that, in 2020, Ellen Mack received the Johns Hopkins University Alumni Association Excellence in Teaching Award and had been on the Peabody piano faculty for more than 50 years.

Even after I completed the doctoral work, Madame K allowed me to sit in on her classes. My secret goal was to be able to anticipate in my mind what she would say in her coaching of each song. Since there are such a myriad of details to be aware of in collaboration, there were always new, often surprising aspects of the music to discover and discuss. I was frequently engaged to play degree recitals at USC, most often, difficult modern works for saxophone and piano. After attending one of those recitals, Mrs. Koldofsky requested that the opportunity to learn and perform that repertoire be reserved for students currently enrolled in the collaborative piano program. After that, I was seldom on campus, but Mrs. Koldofsky and I exchanged occasional newsy, warm and supportive letters until shortly before she passed away.

My seven-year-old son was troubled when I walked in the graduation ceremony in a black robe with the elegant pink doctor of music hood. He looked up and said, “You are not a doctor. You don’t fix sick people.” I answered, “No, I fix sick music!” I have been doing that ever since. A few days later, Mrs. Koldofsky responded to the telephone request from Wendell Nelson, then Chair of the Music Department at the University of California Santa Barbara, by recommending me for their temporary opening in collaborative piano (1979-80). It was with great pleasure that I shared with the piano majors the insights and

collaborative skills I had learned under her tutelage. The students were outstanding but did not appreciate my challenge when I doubled the former class requirement of preparing just one major work per quarter to two major works each quarter. I explained that there had been reports from professional collaborative pianists that it would have been more helpful to their careers to have been introduced to more repertoire in college classes rather than spending so much time mastering each work. In my master classes with Brooks Smith at USC, we had been required to prepare a new major work weekly, or at least one substantial movement.

As a visiting artist at several universities, I presented on sightreading and collaborative piano. When clarinetist Yehuda Gilad and I toured universities along the Rocky Mountains in January 1979, we performed duo concerts and gave master classes and workshops. We were both surprised to realize that the faculty were unfamiliar with the artistic collaborative principles we were coaching, such as, for instance, agreeing on and synchronizing the ebb and flow in musical phrases, and how the pianist can support the singer by discreetly moving the tempo under an especially long vocal phrase or sustained note.

I applied for positions at a few universities in the Los Angeles area but no full-time position developed there. I celebrated the offers Jean Barr and Martin Katz received for the coveted few available fulltime positions. I decided that I would continue as an adjunct faculty member and be active as a freelance performer. I contemplated making a contribution to the field of collaborative keyboard by writing a practical text. I had already devoured the informative books, mostly in the style of "out of my life and times", by Gerald Moore, Robert Spiller, and a few other veteran accompanists. My idea was to create something in a spiral bound format that would lay flat against the music stand so the pianist could study and play the music examples on the keyboard. The book could be used in private lessons and also for a classroom of pianists, perhaps in a multi-keyboard piano lab. For five years I had observed Gwendolyn Koldofsky expend tremendous energy to teach the special skills required when collaborating with vocalists to each individual solo pianist. With each piano/vocal duo she discussed both the artistic nuances in each art song, while also covering basic considerations of collaboration. Before the music department was relocated to Ramo Hall on the main campus of USC from the Clark House, a beloved former mansion where the Koldofsky studio was the former dining room (see photo), she sometimes coached

one voice/piano duo in her private sessions while lying on the carpet. She attributed her back problems to her years at the piano looking up at the music. I believed that an awareness of musical concepts such as texture, color and balance, and of basic collaborative skills like listening, responsive and synchronizing skills, could be learned from a book and illustrated with brief musical examples from the literature. I believed that veteran artist teachers would then be able to focus their limited time and energy on the artistic insights in specific repertoire that they knew intimately from their own performance careers. After editing, primarily by Karen Lynn Davidson Ph.D. (English) and Pauline Alderman Ph.D. (Musicology), the book was ready to publish. I gave the preliminary draft to “Marty” Katz and invited him to write a Forward. He did read the book, but declined the invitation, saying that he was saving his opinions for the book that he, himself, was planning to write. His book, *The Complete Collaborato* (Oxford 2009) was published eighteen years later. My book, *Accompanying Skills for Pianists*, was published first in 1991, with a second edition in 2006 (Culver Crest).

Over the years I became aware that *Accompanying Skills for Pianists* was seldom used by veteran artists for their students as I had envisioned. Several professionals penned glowing reviews; many sat in corners to study my book for an hour or two at State and National music teachers’ conventions, but only a few ordered it for their classes. Perhaps they had their own vision of how they wanted to teach collaboration. Hundreds of teachers in smaller departments, however, made recurrent orders each semester. Perhaps those instructors were looking for teaching helps for their students. Although there has been no further promotion by the publisher, books in both printed and Pdf formats continued to be ordered each year from Culver Crest Publications. <http://culvercrest.com>

In my first class with Madame K at USC, I was assigned to partner with another doctoral candidate, baritone Dale Morich. He sang on three of my doctoral recitals, one a joint doctoral recital of French mélodies and cycles by Faure and Debussy. In our many lecture recitals on art songs, both on and off campuses throughout Southern California, and on tour in Utah, Dale and I performed a wide array of songs and cycles by Schubert, Schumann, Brahms, Strauss, Duparc, Wolf, Ravel, and others. His mellifluous voice, superb diction, and stylistic authority created a very high level of artistic music making. He always insisted that audiences have the complete text printed in the original language side by side with the English translation. I was surprised later to discover that the song cycles,

such as *La Bonne Chanson*, that I had struggled with when I first learned them in the key for baritone, were much more playable in their original keys. Dale was the first collaborative artist who requested that I compose a song for him: "A Dad's Prayer." We included it on several programs, sometimes on Father's Day, when we traveled across town quickly from chapel to chapel for multiple services.

After leaving USC, I continued performing with the Pinkston-Lynn-Price Piano Trio, with baritone Dale Morich, and free-lanced, collaborating with individual vocalists and instrumentalists in California and the Western States. Then, for varying numbers of years I toured nationally and internationally and recorded on the Cambria label as an ensemble member: *Echosphere Duo* (1980's) with Paul Stewart, saxophone; *Echosphere Quartet* (early 1990's) with Ayke Agus, violin and piano, Darryl Taylor, tenor; Douglas Masek, saxophone and clarinet and me as pianist and composer; and *Price Duo* (late 1990's-2012, 2019) with my clarinetist son, Berkeley (D.M.A. Eastman School of Music). Working with Berkeley on an artistic level and learning from his creative insight was very special. Many of my partners requested that I compose for them and we always included at least one of my works on our eclectic programs. My composing kept increasing and it was becoming impossible also to be preparing new repertoire by other composers. Following our last international tour (Hong Kong 2012) my duo partner son wisely advised me that I had time only to prepare my own works and that I needed to discontinue performing music by other composers. It is interesting to me that, even in my current era of focusing on my own works, Mrs. Koldofsky's influence continues to weigh on me, as evidenced by my several song cycles: *Cartoonland* (D. N. Price), *To the Children of War* (Maya Angelou), *Two Songs* (Walt Whitman), *Love Songs* (Robert T. Bowen), *To All Women Everywhere* (Carol Lynn Pearson), *Spiritual Songs* (various), *Four Medieval Songs* (various), *Ludwig's Letter to Eternal Beloved* (Beethoven), *Gallery* (James Morehead). All are published by Culver Crest Publications, released on Cambria albums, and widely available on the internet.

In April 1982, as part of The Second International Congress on Women in Music hosted by the University of Southern California, and chaired by Jeannie G. Pool, President of ICWM, I organized a Symposium of Women Accompanists. There were two sections: Part I: Symposium on Training and Employment Opportunities for Accompanists; and Part 2 Musical Samplings from the Accompanying Literature by Women. The symposium began by recognizing Gwendolyn Koldofsky with a Certificate of Honor for her pioneering work in establishing degrees in

piano accompanying. Panelists, chaired by Deon Nielsen Price, included Jean Barr, Zita Carno, Margaret Emmons, Pia Gilbert, Joanna Grauer, Pearl Kaufman, Natalie Limonick, Henrietta Pelta, Barbara Poper, Delores Stevens, Laraine Stiver, and former western Regional Manager of Hurok Concerts, Paul Lundberg. As I recall Mrs. Koldofsky also participated on the panel. Attached are Pdf files of pages about the symposium from *Source Readings from the International Congress on Women in Music* (Jaygayle Music, 2019 that I requested from the publisher. They contain the program and bios of the participants. (The entire 5-day event was recorded on cassette tapes that were given to then librarian Rodney Rolfs for USC archives. I believe I have a digitalized recording of at least part of the accompanying symposium on accompanying. Lance Bowling at Cambria Recordings may have audio of the entire symposium. He may also have digitalized recordings of all the USC concerts.)

A couple of years prior to her retirement in 1988, Mrs. Koldofsky invited me, and also Brooks Smith, with whom I had worked on piano/instrumental collaboration, to attend her dress rehearsal where she was collaborating with a fine tenor (Michael Sells?). She was feeling somewhat insecure on having been required to prepare and perform a new song cycle in her 80's. Later, when I asked her how the concert went, she said it was all right but she would like to have played it a second time.

Gwendolyn Koldofsky has been a continuing influence on my activity as a performing and recording artist, author, composer, teacher, and in meeting life's challenges. I am grateful most of all for the beauty she revealed to me, especially in art songs. That beauty lingers in my inner ear. I always learned the text well and often recited it while playing. I loved playing the piano accompaniments, even without the singer present. In my inner ear I could hear the sound of her/his voice and their emotional expression. I appreciated that listeners can experience emotional healing vicariously through song. When a couple I knew tragically lost one of their young children, Mahler's evocative *Kindertotenlieder* proved deeply therapeutic, helping them to express their grief and to heal.

—Arroyo Grande, California November, 2024.